

The politics of YouTube: Italian fascism explained by the algorithm

Research Report 1

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Introduction

Recent Italian political developments have become the gravitational centre of global debates. The 2022 elections that have seen Giorgia Meloni - leader of the Fratelli d'Italia's party - as the new Prime Minister have been discussed extensively, especially in the online sphere. The new Italian leader, representative of the far-right, has been indeed associated with what media and the public Internet have worldwide identified as the Rise of the New Italian Fascism.

In the digital realm, algorithms also play a role in framing public issues, and research has shown that they have the potential for shaping political speech and addressing democratic problems (Bucher 2016). In particular, the object of this research is to investigate the political power of YouTube algorithms. Often criticized for their radicalization power, YouTube recommendation algorithms continuously spark debate around their societal and political implications (Kaiser and Rauchfleisch 2019).

This paper focuses on the algorithms' depiction of the controversial debate around fascism and its modern aftermaths, intended as "a hyper-nationalist, anti-parliamentary, anti-liberal [...] movement with the aim of national- social integration through a single party [...] to gain power with totalitarian goals by a combination of legal and violent tactics" (Linz 1976, 24). The aim of this paper is therefore to explore how a contentious topic like "fascism" is framed by YouTube algorithms through the analysis of the Italian case study using the search query "fascism in Italy" both in Italian and in English, and to what extent algorithms lead the users towards more radicalized content following related recommendations on the subject.

Finally, I claim that recommendation systems "suggest" not only videos, but also how to think about a specific controversial issue, furthering demonstrating the inner tendency of YouTube algorithms of pushing viewers towards more negative and violent content (Kaiser and Rauchfleisch 2019).

Theoretical Framework

This paper builds on the notion that algorithms play an active role in the societal sphere (Bucher 2016). The idea that non-human actors take part in socio-technical networks, affecting social realities (Volontè 2017), is one of the foundational concepts of the Actor-Network Theory by Bruno Latour (2005). The aim of this theory is to remove any border drawn between domains in order to obtain a greater understanding of how the elements of these domains are intertwined in the material world (Latour 2005). In this context, there is no distinction between human and non-human elements. In media studies, technology, and subsequently algorithms, are understood as nonhuman actants with

agency in the societal network (Storms 2019). Algorithms can be comprehended as “assemblages, in which human and nonhuman intertwine” (Storms 2019, 6).

The focus of this research is on YouTube recommendation systems, viz the algorithms that “suggest” videos according to a specific search query. YouTube algorithms have extensively been accused of radicalization, therefore of having “a role in guiding content, and to some extent, preferences towards more extremist predispositions” (Ledwich and Zaitsev 2019). Nevertheless, the extreme topics and preferences I refer to in this paper are not explicitly violent materials (e.g., child porn or beheading videos), but hate speech, politically partisan content, revolutionary or conspiracy videos, and misinformation (Ledwich and Zaitsev 2019). Indeed, as YouTube community guidelines remark, “YouTube also regards content containing violent or dangerous content such as hate speech, extremist content, [...] and misinformation as a violation of community guidelines and policies” (YouTube community guidelines, n.d.).

However, as research by Kim et al. (2012) has shown, YouTube is also widely employed for informational purposes. Ledwich and Zaitsev (2019) also highlighted how oftentimes the algorithms tend to push users towards more neutral and even deradicalizing content. In this paper, I refer more generally to this type of content as “informative”.

Method

The method employed in this research draws from algorithms studies. More specifically, it makes use both of issue analysis and radicalization research. As my question focuses on algorithm effect, I conduct a network analysis to identify the recurring patterns of recommenders’ suggestions on results page. Data analysed are retrieved from YouTube’s API through YouTube Data Tools (2015) and visualized on Gephi, a visualization and exploration tool (2009).

The search query “fascism in Italy” is used on YouTube Data Tools to obtain a totality of results for the settings: iteration 1, crawl depth 1. Since my analysis also includes a comparison, the first scraping settings are set to default for location and language (the default location provided by the scraper is the United States), while second ones are set to Italy, getting results also from videos in

Italian (therefore, the search query changes into “fascismo in Italia”). Two graphs are generated on Gephi using the ForceAtlas 2 algorithm (see Fig.1 and Fig.2).

Figure 1: network obtained from the search query “fascism in Italy”, default location, default language

Figure 2: network obtained from the search query “fascismo in Italia”, language: Italian, location: Italy

Communities are identified as follows accordingly to the video’s title, content, and creators through their modularity class. Outliers are not taken into consideration.

Network 1: Fascism in Italy

0	(20.99%)
6	(12.22%)
1	(10.88%)
5	(9.82%)
8	(9.65%)
15	(9.18%)
9	(4.39%)
14	(2.81%)

- 0. Informative/explanatory videos about the 20th century
- 6. Giorgia Meloni and Ignazio La Russa
- 1. Rise of new extremisms in the world
- 5. Extreme content (news)

- 8. Benito Mussolini and other negative historical figures
- 15. World wars and fascism's explanations
- 9. US focused news
- 14. Lower with Crowder

Network 2: Fascismo in Italia

	3	(24.34%)
	0	(16.33%)
	5	(14.21%)
	6	(14.14%)
	2	(8.82%)
	1	(4.23%)
	12	(3.72%)
	11	(3.43%)

- 3. Fascism history and explanations
- 0. Italian history facts
- 5. Giorgia Meloni
- 6. Contemporary fascist waves in Italy
- 2. Alessandro Barbero
- 1. scrip
- 12. Faccetta Nera and other fascist anthems
- 11. GioPizzi

Subsequently, it is inquired how the network is clustered, employing close reading for a totality of 2 videos per community. Most watched videos are taken under scrutiny. Links to selected videos are listed in Appendix A. The selection resulted in a sample of 18 videos for Network 1 and 16 videos for Network 2. The tagging process employed by Ledwich et al. (2019, 2022) in their radicalization research was implemented to categorize videos either as “Radicalized” or as “Informative”. Inspiration was also taken from research by Vitadhani et al. (2021), Beleslin et al. (2017) for the radicalization tags and from the study of Kim et al. (2012) for the informative content tags. Content applying to more tags from a category was classified as part of it. Content that did not classify neither as radicalized nor as informative was identified. The classification was carried out as exemplified in Table 1.

Table 1

Content tags	Category
Conspiracy (promotes conspiracy theories)	Radicalized content
Partisan (focus on political and critical of opposition)	
Revolutionary (endorses the overthrow of the current political system)	
Provocateur (offending and attention grabbing, controversial irony)	
Misinformation (clickbait titles, deceiving thumbnails)	
Educational (focus on educational material)	Informative content
Source-based information	
Presence of professionals	
Impartial position	

Accordingly, the presence of respectively radicalized and informative content is visualized through pie charts realized on Excel after being expressed as percentages. One pie chart is created for every network (see Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Figure 3

Figure 4

Finally, further analysis is conducted on videos regarding Giorgia Meloni from respective clusters from both networks. Using the same categorization procedure, 10 videos in total are selected from the two networks for close reading. The presence of radicalized content is assessed as in Table 1 (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5

Analysis

The analysis of the two networks and their 17 communities highlighted the prominence of content about historical fascism in Italy and Benito Mussolini. Indeed, communities labeled as “Informative/Explanatory videos about the 20th century”, “Benito Mussolini and other negative historical figures” and “World wars and fascism’s explanations” in Network 1, and “Fascism history and explanations” and “Italian history facts” in Network 2 are the ones that compose the biggest part of the networks (a totality of, respectively 39.82% and 40.67%).

Most of these videos are categorized as “Informative”. For example, the author of the video “Il Partito Nazionale Fascista” (Il Diario di Charlotte) presented the topic in an impartial way, discussing source-based information referenced in the description of the video (see Fig. 6).

Figure 6

However, what is interesting about these communities is that not all of them are clustered together towards the center of the network, even though they are similar in content to each other. For example, the community of Network 1 labeled “World wars and fascism’s explanations” is much more marginal and detached from the rest of the network, meaning that it is less likely that the user looking for “fascism in Italy” will end up watching the videos it contains.

Instead, communities of videos about Giorgia Meloni or Ignazio La Russa (current President of the Senate in Italy) are not only particularly present in both networks (they represent 12.22% of Network 1 and 14.21% of Network 2) but also relatively central in Network 1, being also the second most prominent community. What emerges from this observation is that users looking for “fascism in Italy” are almost immediately redirected towards video discussing Giorgia Meloni and the current Italian political situation, even though both have no explicit connection with historical fascism nor other kinds of extremisms. Moreover, the videos of these communities are mainly radicalized, as

shown by the pie charts obtained (see Fig. 5). For instance, some of them show deceiving titles, claiming that “fascism is back in Italy”, when there is no public disclosed link of sort (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7

Moreover, most of the videos analyzed presented information in a partisan and provocative way (Ledwich et al. 2019, 2022). In one of the videos from Network 2, for instance, the YouTuber states clearly (in Italian) that his position is not impartial (Saverio Tommasi, “Processo a Saviano: perché ho detto “Bastardi, come avete potuto” a Giorgia Meloni e Matteo Salvini”, 0:40).

What results from this examination is that not only recommendation systems implicitly frame public and often controversial issues, but also that they incentivize radicalization and polarization. Indeed, in Network 1, the user who gets recommended videos from the community labeled “Giorgia Meloni and Ignazio la Russa” is more easily drawn towards more radicalized content, such as “Extreme content (news)” and videos regarding the rise of new extremisms in the world, which is still considered as strong content (YouTube community guidelines, n.d.) (see Fig. 8).

Figure 8

According to Ledwich and Zaitsev (2019), this phenomenon is called “Radical Bubbles” (3). More specifically, “recommendations influence viewers of radical content to watch more similar

content than they would otherwise, making it less likely that alternative views are presented” (Ledwich and Zaitsev 2019, 3). The more the users are drawn towards the radicalized content, the more it is difficult for them to get out of this loop.

Several communities from both networks host mainly videos from one Youtuber, as some clusters’ names are assigned according to the creator (e.g., “Lower with Crowder” in Network 1 and “GioPizzi” in Network 2). Even if some of them contain impartial or educative information, therefore being categorized as “informative”, others contain clickbait titles, provocative and aggressive language, becoming part of the aforementioned “Radical Bubbles” (Ledwich and Zaitsev 2019, 3). In one of his videos, for example, the Italian YouTuber GioPizzi gives his opinion on Giorgia Meloni’s discourse on homo-parenthood (GioPizzi, “Perchè il discorso di GIORGIA MELONI è DELIRANTE”). His explanation contains lots of sarcasm, mockery and even insults - he refers to far-right sustainers as “monkeys” (GioPizzi, “Perchè il discorso di GIORGIA MELONI è DELIRANTE”, 4:01) - and, drawing from his arguments, his position towards the current Italian government is hostile.

Finally, from a general observation emerges a disparity between the quality of the videos of the two networks. Not only the qualitative content analysis of the videos and the resulting pie charts, but also the semantical difference in the labels’ names, highlights the predomination of radicalized content in the Network obtained from US data compared to the one obtained from Italian data. However, this is not surprising as Tiffen et al. (2014) have already stressed, in their comparative study on the news, how information variance is a common pattern across different countries, in relation to the number, type, quality and use of sources.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to study the YouTube algorithms’ framing of the 2022 Italian political elections and their association with the notion of “fascism”. This research wanted to investigate the radicalized nature of YouTube algorithms and to what extent the user was drawn towards more violent and/or deceiving content following the path suggested by the recommender systems. Building on the Actor Network Theory by Latour (2005) and on the data obtained from my network and content analysis, I demonstrated how algorithms have a strong role in outlining specific political viewpoints, especially concerning delicate issues. Accordingly, my analysis has shown how users are kept into polarized bubbles that prevent them from being exposed to alternative views (Ledwich and Zaitsev 2019). Moreover, I assessed the radicalizing tendency of the platform, which attracts users towards more extreme content, also comparing the influence of location settings in the two networks.

As radicalization research is a relatively new field, further research could employ a different methodology in the study of the radicalizing nature of the platform, as well as the online controversial debate on fascism and other political and social issues.

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Appendix A

Network 1	
<i>Class</i>	<i>Links selected</i>
Informative/explanatory videos about the 20th century	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mGRuN-6Xh0c • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gmZDvy3JiB0
Giorgia Meloni and Ignazio La Russa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=21JVkyZfBGc • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j6S0XLoznZg
Rise of new extremisms in the world	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M0ZhbCRpmfY • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wgHjo7ac3nc
Extreme content (news)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bW04FsXpZV8 • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOIRdkIIfRg
Benito Mussolini and other negative historical figures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e_2of8pmHYU • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yfFvB70TIrw
World wars and fascism's explanations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tQIMtoDp8ks • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OvDsvHNvVZw
US focused news	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_vMLAwjQpB8 • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ep2n2oIHtpI
Lower with Crowder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jNNIq3EfgCI • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kC22-s8rTxc

Network 2	
<i>Class</i>	<i>Links selected</i>
Fascism history and explanations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FGyG5Ec2p3Y • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZmsfTycKH28
Italian history facts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eyBdxtCPZ2U • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O2wrHIFQwRE
Giorgia Meloni	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOTwXv8HrSM • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JvwuNLR9SHg
Contemporary fascist waves in Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WgkKMKjXN5E • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=priGNmLvGc0
Alessandro Barbero	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xumfir54xb4 • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q-g34chQH5Y
scrip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TnjZnqLLhQA • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vts3IV1ZS5Y

Faccetta Nera and other fascist anthems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MeYoX6YukmI • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mnigWcQAvKM
GioPizzi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nPNWmUinFCw • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9QaGp8YFh5U

Additional videos related to the Italian elections' topic	
Network 1	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bKjYi3ar7KE
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HglP4WwHJOM
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LGowfUX2ENY
Network 2	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-pXcEAfXe3c
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NcurH0Kr67M
	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-ysAF14rncY